

Appendix 1. PRISMA 2020 checklist ¹.

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	P1
ABSTRACT			
Abstract	2	See the PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts checklist.	P1
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of existing knowledge.	P1L29
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	P2L51
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	5	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for the syntheses.	P2L79
Information sources	6	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies. Specify the date when each source was last searched or consulted.	P3L11
Search strategy	7	Present the full search strategies for all databases, registers and websites, including any filters and limits used.	P3L50
Selection process	8	Specify the methods used to decide whether a study met the inclusion criteria of the review, including how many reviewers screened each record and each report retrieved, whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	P3L98
Data collection process	9	Specify the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data from each report, whether they worked independently, any processes for obtaining or confirming data from study investigators, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	P4L5
Data items	10a	List and define all outcomes for which data were sought. Specify whether all results that were compatible with each outcome domain in each study were sought (e.g. for all measures, time points, analyses), and if not, the methods used to decide which results to collect.	P3L4
	10b	List and define all other variables for which data were sought (e.g. participant and intervention characteristics, funding sources). Describe any assumptions made about any missing or unclear information.	P4L96
Study risk of bias assessment	11	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies, including details of the tool(s) used, how many reviewers assessed each study and whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	P4L16
Effect measures	12	Specify for each outcome the effect measure(s) (e.g. risk ratio, mean difference) used in the synthesis or presentation of results.	P6L11
Synthesis methods	13a	Describe the processes used to decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis (e.g. tabulating the study intervention characteristics and comparing against the planned groups for each synthesis (item #5)).	P4L96
	13b	Describe any methods required to prepare the data for presentation or synthesis, such as handling of missing summary statistics, or data conversions.	P6L7
	13c	Describe any methods used to tabulate or visually display results of	P4L22

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
		individual studies and syntheses.	
	13d	Describe any methods used to synthesize results and provide a rationale for the choice(s). If meta-analysis was performed, describe the model(s), method(s) to identify the presence and extent of statistical heterogeneity, and software package(s) used.	P4L95
	13e	Describe any methods used to explore possible causes of heterogeneity among study results (e.g. subgroup analysis, meta-regression).	P6L24
	13f	Describe any sensitivity analyses conducted to assess robustness of the synthesized results.	P6L24
Reporting bias assessment	14	Describe any methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis (arising from reporting biases).	P4L12
Certainty assessment	15	Describe any methods used to assess certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for an outcome.	P4L70
RESULTS			
Study selection	16a	Describe the results of the search and selection process, from the number of records identified in the search to the number of studies included in the review, ideally using a flow diagram.	P6L39
	16b	Cite studies that might appear to meet the inclusion criteria, but which were excluded, and explain why they were excluded.	P6L47
Study characteristics	17	Cite each included study and present its characteristics.	P6L53
Risk of bias in studies	18	Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.	P7L37
Results of individual studies	19	For all outcomes, present, for each study: (a) summary statistics for each group (where appropriate) and (b) an effect estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval), ideally using structured tables or plots.	P6L53
Results of syntheses	20a	For each synthesis, briefly summarise the characteristics and risk of bias among contributing studies.	P11L13
	20b	Present results of all statistical syntheses conducted. If meta-analysis was done, present for each the summary estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval) and measures of statistical heterogeneity. If comparing groups, describe the direction of the effect.	P11L13
	20c	Present results of all investigations of possible causes of heterogeneity among study results.	P11L13
	20d	Present results of all sensitivity analyses conducted to assess the robustness of the synthesized results.	P11L29
Reporting biases	21	Present assessments of risk of bias due to missing results (arising from reporting biases) for each synthesis assessed.	-
Certainty of evidence	22	Present assessments of certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for each outcome assessed.	P7L58
DISCUSSION			
Discussion	23a	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence.	P11L61
	23b	Discuss any limitations of the evidence included in the review.	P13L10
	23c	Discuss any limitations of the review processes used.	P13L10
	23d	Discuss implications of the results for practice, policy, and future research.	P13L42
OTHER INFORMATION			

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
Registration and protocol	24a	Provide registration information for the review, including register name and registration number, or state that the review was not registered.	P2L73
	24b	Indicate where the review protocol can be accessed, or state that a protocol was not prepared.	P2L73
	24c	Describe and explain any amendments to information provided at registration or in the protocol.	-
Support	25	Describe sources of financial or non-financial support for the review, and the role of the funders or sponsors in the review.	P1L10
Competing interests	26	Declare any competing interests of review authors.	P13L64
Availability of data, code and other materials	27	Report which of the following are publicly available and where they can be found: template data collection forms; data extracted from included studies; data used for all analyses; analytic code; any other materials used in the review.	P13L78

¹This checklist is from: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, *et al.* The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71

Appendix 2. Search formulas and algorithms for the search databases and the clinical trial registration databases.

2-1) MEDLINE (PubMed)

Database: MEDLINE (PubMed)		
The date of the last search: March 4, 2025		
The literature search was performed by an external collaborator, a librarian who was involved in clinical and epidemiological research and has extensive search experience in systematic review.		
#	Search formulas and algorithms	# of journals
#1	"sulforaphane glucosinolate"[tw] OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate"[tiab:-2]	20
#2	"1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane"[Title/Abstract:-0] OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate"[Title/Abstract] OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"[Title/Abstract:-0] OR sulphoraphan*[TW] OR sulforaphan*[TW]	3,280
#3	"sulforaphane" [Supplementary Concept]	1,902
#4	#2 OR #3	3,280
#5	"Glucosinolates"[MeSH] OR Glucosinolate*[tw] OR SGS[tw]	8,121
#6	#4 AND #5	426
#7	"Sulfoxides"[Mesh] OR "Sulfoxides"[tw]	33,841
#8	"Isothiocyanates"[MeSH] OR Isothiocyanate*[tw]	30,516
#9	#7 AND #8	1,914
#10	glucoraphanin[nm] OR glucoraphanin[tw]	483
#11	#1 OR #6 OR #9 OR #10	2,344
#12 [†]	(clinical trial[pt] OR comparative study[pt] OR (control[tw] AND study[tw]) OR program[tw] OR epidemiologic studies[mh]) NOT ((animals[mh:noexp] NOT humans[mh:noexp]) OR comment[pt] OR editorial[pt] OR review[pt] OR meta analysis[pt] OR case report[tw] OR consensus[mh] OR guideline[pt] OR history[sh])	6,104,886
#13	#11 AND #12	247
#14	(randomized controlled trial [pt] OR controlled clinical trial [pt] OR randomized [tiab] OR placebo [tiab] OR clinical trials as topic [mesh:noexp] OR randomly [tiab] OR trial [ti]) NOT (animals [mh] NOT humans [mh])	1,550,233
#15	#11 AND #14	99
#16	#13 OR #15	280

†#12 is from: Waffenschmidt S, Navarro-Ruan T, Hobson N, Hausner E, Sauerland S, Haynes RB. Development and validation of study filters for identifying controlled non-randomized studies in PubMed and Ovid MEDLINE. *Res Synth Methods*. 2020; 11(5): 617-626. doi:10.1002/jrsm.1425 Non-randomized Studies filter best sensitivity

2-2) Ichushi-Web¹

Database: Ichushi-Web		
The date of the last search: February 28, 2025		
The literature search was performed by an external collaborator, a librarian who was involved in clinical and epidemiological research and has extensive search experience in systematic review.		
#	Search formulas and algorithms	# of journals
#1	Sulphoraphane/TH or "Sulphoraphane"/TA or "Sulforaphan"/TA or スルフォラファン/TA or スルフォラフェン/TA or "1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane"/TA or "4-Methylsulphinylbutyl Glucosinolate"/TA or "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"/TA or "Methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"/TA or SFN/TA or 実生/MTH	585
#2	Glucoraphanin/TH or グルコラファニン/TA or Glucoraphanin/TA	24
#3	#1 or #2	604
#4	"Glucosinolates"/TH or "Isothiocyanates"/TH or "Glucosinolates"/TA or グルコシノレート/TA or グルコシノラート/TA or "Isothiocyanates"/TA or イソチオシアネート/TA or イソチアシアン酸類/TA or イソチオシアネート/TA	1,912
#5	SGS/TA or アブラナ科/TH	2,892
#6	#4 or #5	4,590
#7	#3 and #6	348
#8	#7 not ((CK=動物) not (CK=ヒト))	232
#9	(#8) and (PT=会議録除く)	106

¹Ichushi is a bibliographic database that was established in 1903 and is being updated by the Japan Medical Abstracts Society, a non-profit and non-governmental body; therefore, the search formulas and algorithms contain the terms in Japanese.

2-3) Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews (The Cochrane Library/Wiley)

Database: The Cochrane Library/Wiley		
The date of the last search: March 4, 2025		
The literature search was performed by an external collaborator, a librarian who was involved in clinical and epidemiological research and has extensive search experience in systematic review.		
#	Search formulas and algorithms	# of journals
#1	sulforaphane NEXT/6 glucosinolat*:ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews	0
#2	("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulphoraphan* OR sulforaphan*):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews	0
#3	MeSH descriptor: [Glucosinolates] explode all trees in Cochrane Reviews	1
#4	(Glucosinolate* OR SGS):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews	2
#5	#3 OR #4 in Cochrane Reviews	2
#6	#2 AND #5 in Cochrane Reviews	0
#7	MeSH descriptor: [Sulfoxides] explode all trees in Cochrane Reviews	5
#8	(Sulfoxides):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews	2
#9	#7 OR #8 in Cochrane Reviews	6
#10	MeSH descriptor: [Isothiocyanates] explode all trees in Cochrane Reviews	0
#11	(Isothiocyanate*):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews	0
#12	#10 OR #11 in Cochrane Reviews	0
#13	#9 AND #12 in Cochrane Reviews	0
#14	(glucoraphanin*):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews	0
#15	#1 OR #6 OR #13 OR #14 in Cochrane Reviews	0

2-4) Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials(The Cochrane Library/Wiley)

Database: Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (The Cochrane Library/Wiley)		
The date of the last search: March 4, 2025		
The literature search was performed by an external collaborator, a librarian who was involved in clinical and epidemiological research and has extensive search experience in systematic review.		
#	Search formulas and algorithms	# of journals
#1	sulforaphane NEXT/6 glucosinolat*:ti,ab,kw in Trials	13
#2	("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulphoraphan* OR sulforaphan*):ti,ab,kw in Trials	240
#3	MeSH descriptor: [Glucosinolates] explode all trees in Trials	38
#4	(Glucosinolate* OR SGS):ti,ab,kw in Trials	237
#5	#3 OR #4 in Trials	238
#6	#2 AND #5 in Trials	50
#7	MeSH descriptor: [Sulfoxides] explode all trees in Trials	4,889
#8	(Sulfoxides):ti,ab,kw in Trials	298
#9	#7 OR #8 in Trials	4,891
#10	MeSH descriptor: [Isothiocyanates] explode all trees in Trials	115
#11	(Isothiocyanate*):ti,ab,kw in Trials	246
#12	#10 OR #11 in Trials	248
#13	#9 AND #12 in Trials	63
#14	(glucoraphanin*):ti,ab,kw in Trials	63
#15	#1 OR #6 OR #13 OR #14 in Trials	118

2-5) CINAHL with Full Text (EBSCO)

Database: CINAHL with Full Text (EBSCO)		
The date of the last search: August 23, 2023		
The literature search was performed by an external collaborator, a librarian who was involved in clinical and epidemiological research and has extensive search experience in systematic review.		
#	Search formulas and algorithms	# of journals
S1	TI sulforaphane N6 glucosinolat* OR AB sulforaphane N6 glucosinolat* Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	18
S2	TI ((1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphinylbutane OR 4-Methylsulphinylbutyl Glucosinolate OR 4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate OR sulphoraphan* OR sulforaphan*)) OR AB ((1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphinylbutane OR 4-Methylsulphinylbutyl Glucosinolate OR 4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate OR sulphoraphan* OR sulforaphan*))	4,442,928
S3	TI (Glucosinolate* OR SGS) OR AB (Glucosinolate* OR SGS)	534
S4	S2 AND S3	32
S5	(MH "Phytochemicals")	10,957
S6	TI Sulfoxide* OR AB Sulfoxide*	620
S7	TI Isothiocyanate* OR AB Isothiocyanate*	878
S8	(S6 OR S7) AND S5	246
S9	TI glucoraphanin* OR AB glucoraphanin*	50
S10	S1 OR S4 OR S8 OR S9	302
S11	((MH ANIMALS+ NOT (MH HUMAN OR MH "Male")) OR (MH (ANIMAL STUDIES) NOT MH (HUMAN)) OR (TI (ANIMAL MODEL) NOT MH (HUMAN)))	193,677
S12	S10 NOT S11	232

2-6) Global Index Medicus

Database: Global Index Medicus		
The date of the last search: March 4, 2025		
The literature search was performed by an external collaborator, a librarian who was involved in clinical and epidemiological research and has extensive search experience in systematic review.		
#	Search formulas and algorithms	# of journals
#1	tw:("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate")	0
#2	(tw:("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane" OR glucoraphanin))	96
#3	tw:("broccoli seed extract" OR "broccoli seed extracts" OR "broccoli sprout" OR "broccoli sprouts")	6
†Total number of documents after removing duplicates.		91†

2-7) International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP)

Database: International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP)		
The date of the last search: March 6, 2025		
The literature search was performed by an external collaborator, a librarian who was involved in clinical and epidemiological research and has extensive search experience in systematic review.		
#	Search formulas and algorithms	# of records
#1	in the Title (Recruitment status:ALL) ("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate")	0
#2	"1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane" OR glucoraphanin	103 records for 99 trials found!
#3	in the Title (Recruitment status:ALL) ("broccoli seed extract" OR "broccoli seed extracts" OR "broccoli sprout" OR "broccoli sprouts")	52 records for 52 trials found!
#4	in the Intervention (Recruitment status:ALL) ("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate")	5 records for 5 trials found!
#5	in the Intervention (Recruitment status:ALL) ("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane" OR glucoraphanin)	81 records for 77 trials found!
#6	in the Intervention (Recruitment status:ALL) ("broccoli seed extract" OR "broccoli seed extracts" OR "broccoli sprout" OR "broccoli sprouts")	60 records for 60 trials found!
†Total number of records after removing duplicates.		141†

2-8) International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO)

Database: : International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO)		
The date of the last search: February 28, 2025		
The literature search was performed by an external collaborator, a librarian who was involved in clinical and epidemiological research and has extensive search experience in systematic review.		
#	Search formulas and algorithms	# of journals
#1	"sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate"	0
#2	"1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane" OR glucoraphanin	23
#3	"sulforaphane" [Supplementary Concept]	25
†Total number of documents after removing duplicates.		44†

2-9) ClinicalTrials.gov

Database: ClinicalTrials.gov		
The date of the last search: March 4, 2025		
The literature search was performed by an external collaborator, a librarian who was involved in clinical and epidemiological research and has extensive search experience in systematic review.		
#	Search formulas and algorithms	# of journals
#1	Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate")	28
#2	Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane" OR glucoraphanin) AND "Glucosinolates")	19
#3	Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("broccoli seed extract" OR "broccoli seed extracts" OR "broccoli sprout" OR "broccoli sprouts")	68
#4	Intervention/treatment (Recruitment status:ALL) ("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate")	21
#5	Intervention/treatment (Recruitment status:ALL) ("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane" OR glucoraphanin) AND "Glucosinolates")	8
#6	Intervention/treatment (Recruitment status:ALL) ("broccoli seed extract" OR "broccoli seed extracts" OR "broccoli sprout" OR "broccoli sprouts")	62
Total number of documents after removing duplicates.		81

2-10) University Hospital Medical Information Network-Clinical Trials Registry (UMIN-CTR)¹

Database: University Hospital Medical Information Network-Clinical Trials Registry (UMIN-CTR)		
The date of the last search: March 6, 2025		
The literature search was performed by an external collaborator, a librarian who was involved in clinical and epidemiological research and has extensive search experience in systematic review.		
#	Search formulas and algorithms	# of journals
#1	検索：目的1 スルフォラファングルコシノレート	1
#2	検索：目的1 sulforaphane glucosinolate	0
#3	検索：目的1 Sulphoraphane	0
#4	検索：目的1 スルフォラファン	12
#5	検索：目的1 スルフォラフェン	0
#6	検索：目的1 Glucoraphanin	0
#7	検索：目的1 グルコラファニン	0
#8	検索：目的1 ブロココリスプラウト	1
#9	検索：目的1 BS抽出物	0
#10	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード スルフォラファングルコシノレート	3
#11	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード sulforaphane glucosinolate	2
#12	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード Sulphoraphane	0
#13	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード スルフォラファン	18
#14	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード スルフォラフェン	0
#15	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード Glucoraphanin	0
#16	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード グルコラファニン	0
#17	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード ブロココリスプラウト	2
#18	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード BS抽出物	0
†Total number of documents after removing duplicates.		19†

¹UMIN-CTR is the first clinical trial registration system in Japan; therefore, the search formulas and algorithms contain the terms in Japanese.

Appendix 3. Detailed explanations for certainty assessment ratings.

Items	Explanations
The risk of bias in individual studies	We judged the risk of bias at three levels: low risk of bias (0), mod-erate risk of bias (-1), and high risk of bias (-2).
The indirectness of each article	Two reviewers (S.Sa. and S.Sh.) independently assessed the indirectness. We scored each item as follows: "there is no indirectness" (+), "there is an indirectness," or "unclear" (-). Based on the total number of (-), each study was evaluated as follows: 0, indicating low indirectness (0); 1, indicating moderate indirectness (-1); and 2-5, indicating high indirectness (-2). Any uncertainties or disagreements regarding the indirectness were discussed with another author (S.T.) and resolved.
Imprecision	Imprecision was evaluated based on the total sample sizes of the included studies. Based on the total sample size, we evaluated imprecision as follows: ≥ 100 , precise (0); 40-99, moderately imprecise (-1); and ≤ 39 , highly imprecise (-2).
Inconsistencies	Inconsistencies were evaluated using I^2 values calculated from the forest plots. We judged the inconsistencies at three levels: 0%-40%, low inconsistency (0); 41%-70%, moderate inconsistency (-1); and 71%-100%, high inconsistency (-2).
Publication bias	Publication bias was evaluated by visual inspection of funnel plots and by Begg's test ($p < 0.05$ indicated a significant difference). We judged the publication bias at three levels: low publication bias (0), moderate publication bias (-1), and high publication bias (-2).
Certainty of the evidence	The total sum was defined as the certainty of the evidence. We judged the total sum at four levels: -2 to 0 indicates that the certainty of the evidence is "high (A)"; -5 to -3 indicates that the certainty of the evidence is "medium (B)"; -8 to -6 indicates that the certainty of the evidence is "low (C); and -10 to -9 indicates that the certainty of the evidence is "very low (D)". If the certainty of the evidence was A or B, then the evidence was judged to have a scientific basis.

Appendix 4. The results of the peer review using the PRESS checklist.

4-1) MEDLINE (PubMed)¹

<p>Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher</p>	
<p>Searcher: The literature search was performed by an external collaborator, a librarian who was involved in clinical and epidemiological research and has extensive search experience in systematic review.</p>	
<p>Date submitted: 2023/08/05</p>	<p>Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.</p>
<p>Search Topic or Title:</p>	
<p>SGS (スルフォラファングルコシノレート) による肝機能の維持・改善作用</p>	
<p>This search strategy is:</p>	
<p>My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:</p>	
<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This is my first submission</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> This is submitted after feedback</p>
<p>This search strategy is:</p>	
<p>My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:</p>	
<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This is my first submission</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> This is submitted after feedback</p>
<p>Database(s):(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): [mandatory]</p>	
<p>MEDLINE</p>	
<p>Database Platform(s):(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): [mandatory]</p>	
<p>PubMed</p>	
<p>*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:</p>	
<p>Research Question(s)</p>	
<p>(Describe the purpose of the search) [mandatory]</p>	
<p>健常成人を対象として、SGS を含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取と比較して、肝機能を維持・改善するか</p>	
<p>PICO(S) or Related Format:(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)</p>	
<p>P 健常成人</p>	
<p>I SGS を含む食品の経口摂取</p>	
<p>C 同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取</p>	

- O** 肝機能を維持・改善
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

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*** sulforaphane ***
1      "sulforaphane" [Supplementary Concept]          1,730
2      "1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphinylbutane"[Title/Abstract::~0] OR "4-Methylsulphinylbutyl Glucosinolate"[Title/Abstract]
OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"[Title/Abstract::~0] OR sulforafan[Title/Abstract] OR "sulforaphane"[tiab]
2,790
3      #1 OR #2    2,880
*** glucoraphanin とかけあわせ***
4      "glucoraphanin" [tw]    424
5      #3 AND #4    255
*** ブロッコリーとかけあわせ***
6      "broccoli seed extract"[tiab] OR "broccoli seed extracts"[tiab::~0] OR "broccoli sprout"[tiab] OR "broccoli sprouts"[tiab]
328
7      #6 AND #3          218
8      9548634[tw]        3 //PubChem CID
9      ("SFN"[tiab] AND "SGS"[tiab]) AND "Sulforaphane"[tw]    3
10     "sulforaphane glucosinolates"[tiab::~0] OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate"[tw]    11
11     #5 OR #7 OR #8 OR #9 OR #10    405
12     animals [mh] NOT humans [mh]          5,142,638
13     #11 NOT #12          335

```

Key articles: 2018321874, 36618707, CN-02550556(CENTRAL)

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Peer review was performed by an external collaborator, a medical librarian with extensive search experience in systematic review.

Date completed: 2023/08/17

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

1. Sulforaphane と glucoraphanin は類義語に近い捉え方で OR 検索ではいかがでしょうか。

2. #2 末尾の2つについて、意図されているのでしたら構いませんが、sulforafan はヒット2件程なので変更もありかと思えます。 sulforafan[Title/Abstract] OR "sulforaphane"[tiab] →例：sulphoraphan*[TW] OR sulforaphan*[TW]
3. 今回ブロッコリースプラウトに限定しないということでサプリ等も含むとすると、Sulforaphane AND (ブロッコリー OR #8 OR #9 OR #10) ですとやや限定的になるように思います。

○#6 植物で掛け合わせる場合、アブラナ科に広げてはいかがでしょうか。

例："Brassicaceae"[MeSH] OR cruciferous[tw] OR crucifera*[tw] OR "broccoli"*[tw] OR "brassica"*[tw]

○アブラナ科植物以外（サプリ等？）を拾う目的で、#8～#10に加えて、Sulforaphane と掛け合わせる条件を複数設けた方が漏れ防止のためより安心かと思いましたが、いかがでしょうか。（ノイズ等を十分確認できていませんが・・・）

・ "glucosinolates"[MeSH Terms] OR "glucosinolate"*[Text Word] OR "SGS"[tiab]

・ ("isothiocyanates"[MeSH] OR "isothiocyanate"*[Text Word]) AND ("sulfoxides"[MeSH] OR "sulfoxide"*[Text Word])

理由：sulforaphane の臨床試験文献ではこの2つのmhがセットで含まれることが多いように思い、例示しましたが、物質名などを理解していないため、この掛け合わせが適当なのか不明です。上記を Sulforaphane と掛け合わせると、PMID: 35010950, 28112972（今回該当するか分かりませんが）を拾います。

4. 1～3の検索ですと2000件程になるので、研究デザインでの絞込みが必要になりそうです。

当初の検索の300件は程良い件数だと思います。全体として、ノイズ等も考慮してご検討いただけたらありがたいです。中途半端なフィードバックで恐縮です。よろしくお願いいたします。

¹The literature search and the peer review in this study were performed by two external Japanese collaborators; therefore, the suggestions and/or requests to each other were provided in Japanese.

4-2) Ichushi-Web¹**Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher**

Searcher: The literature search was performed by an external collaborator, a librarian who was involved in clinical and epidemiological research and has extensive search experience in systematic review.

Date submitted: 2023/08/05

Date requested by: [Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

Search Topic or Title:

SGS (スルフォラフアングルコシノレート) による肝機能の維持・改善作用

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s): (e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

Ichushi-Web

Database Platform(s): (e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

健康成人を対象として、SGS を含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取と比較して、肝機能を維持・改善するか

PICO(S) or Related Format: (Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

P 健康成人

I SGS を含む食品の経口摂取

- C 同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取
- O 肝機能を維持・改善
- S Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 "sulforaphane glucosinolate"/TA or スルフォラファングルコシノレート/TA [2 件]
 #2 Sulphoraphane/TH [275 件]
 #3 "Sulphoraphane"/TA or "Sulforafan"/TA or スルフォラファン/TA or スルフォラフェン/TA or "1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane"/TA or "4-Methylsulphinylbutyl Glucosinolate"/TA or "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"/TA or "Methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"/TA [149 件]
 #4 #1 or #2 or #3 [289 件]
 #5 "Glucosinolates"/TH [47 件]
 #6 "Glucosinolates"/TA or グルコシノレート/TA [16 件]
 #7 #5 or #6 [55 件]
 #8 "Isothiocyanates"/TH [1,627 件]
 #9 "Isothiocyanates"/TA or イソチオシアネート/TA or イソチアシアン酸類/TA or イソチオシアナート/TA [372 件]
 #10 #8 or #9 [1,776 件]
 #11 #7 or #10 [1,818 件]
 #12 #4 and #11 [258 件]
 #13 ブロッコリスプラウト/TA or "BS 抽出物"/TA [4 件]
 #14 "SFN"/TA and "SGS"/TA [2 件]
 #15 #12 or #13 or #14 [261 件]
 #16 (#15) and (PT=会議録除く) [97 件]
 #17 (CK=動物) not (CK=ヒト) [915,864 件]
 #18 #16 not #17 [76 件]

Key articles: 2018321874, 36618707

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Peer review was performed by an external collaborator, a medical librarian with extensive search experience in systematic review.

Date completed: 2023/08/15

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

#3 "Sulphoraphane"/TA or "Sulforaphan"/TA or スルフォラファン/TA or スルフォラフェン/TA or "1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane"/TA or "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate"/TA or "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"/TA or "Methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"/TA [149 件]

→ 【案（黄色箇所）】 "Sulphoraphane"/TA or "Sulforaphan"/TA or スルフォラファン/TA or スルフォラフェン/TA or "1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane"/TA or "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate"/TA or "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"/TA or "Methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"/TA or SFN/TA or 実生/MTH or Glucoraphanin/TH or グルコラファンin/TA

※グルコラファンinは、素人（私）が少し調べたところ、スルフォラファンの前駆体とのことで、検索に加えてもよいのではという気がしましたが、いかがでしょうか。また、加える場合、スルフォラファンの類義語として含めてよいのでしょうか。恐れ入りますが、依頼者に照会の必要があるようでしたらお手数をおかけします。

（日本語検索では結果件数に影響しませんが、他のDBの参考に、念のため確認できればと思います。）

#11に追加で、"or SGS/TA or アブラナ科/TH"を足していただくと、#13, #14が不要になります。

（#13, #14について、思考プロセスを追えず恐れ入ります。若干付け加え的な感じがしたので、本体の掛け合わせに含められないか検討しました。以下に例示しますが、当初ご提案のうち1件が漏れます。ご検討お願いできますでしょうか。）

(((((Sulphoraphane/TH or "sulforaphane glucosinolate"/TA or スルフォラファングルコシノレート/TA or "Sulphoraphane"/TA or "Sulforaphan"/TA or スルフォラファン/TA or スルフォラフェン/TA or "1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane"/TA or "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate"/TA or "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"/TA or "Methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"/TA or SFN/TA or 実生/MTH or Glucoraphanin/TH or グルコラファンin/TA) and ("Glucosinolates"/TH or "Isothiocyanates"/TH or "Glucosinolates"/TA or グルコシノレート/TA or グルコシノレート/TA or "Isothiocyanates"/TA or イソチオシアネート/TA or イソチアシアン酸類/TA or イソチオシアネート/TA or SGS/TA or アブラナ科/TH)) not ((CK=動物) not (CK=ヒト))) and (PT=会議録除く)) 94 件 2023/8/15 現在

¹The literature search and the peer review in this study were performed by two external Japanese collaborators; therefore, the suggestions and/or requests to each other were provided in Japanese.

4-3) Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews (The Cochrane Library/Wiley)¹**Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher**

Searcher: The literature search was performed by an external collaborator, a librarian who was involved in clinical and epidemiological research and has extensive search experience in systematic review.

Date submitted: 2023/08/05

Date requested by: [Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

Search Topic or Title:

SGS (スルフォラファングルコシノレート) による肝機能の維持・改善作用

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s):(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

Cochrane Reviews: Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews

Database Platform(s):(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

The Cochrane Library(Wiley)

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

健全成人を対象として、SGSを含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取と比較して、肝機能を維持・改善するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

P 健全成人

- I** SGS を含む食品の経口摂取
- C** 同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取
- O** 肝機能を維持・改善
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

```
#1 (sulforaphane NEXT glucosinolate*):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews 0
#2 ((broccoli NEXT seed NEXT extract*) OR (broccoli NEXT sprout*)):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews 0
#3 ("glucora phanin" OR glucoraphanin*):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews 0
#4 (sulforaphane):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews 0
#5 ("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphinylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphinylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane"):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews 0
#6 #4 OR #5 in Cochrane Reviews 0
#7 #2 AND #6 in Cochrane Reviews 0
#8 (glucoraphanin):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews 0
#9 #6 AND #8 in Cochrane Reviews 0
#10 (SFN AND SGS):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews 0
#11 #1 OR #7 OR #9 OR #10 in Cochrane Reviews 0
```

Key articles: 2018321874, 36618707=10.3389/fnut.2022.1077271(DOI)=CN-02550556(CENTRAL)

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Peer review was performed by an external collaborator, a medical librarian with extensive search experience in systematic review.

Date completed: 2023/08/17

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example: 検索ありがとうございます。

CENTRAL と共通の検索式で、絞込み (in Cochrane Reviews) を設定していただけたらと思います。ゼロ件でした。

¹The literature search and the peer review in this study were performed by two external Japanese collaborators; therefore, the suggestions and/or requests to each other were provided in Japanese.

4-4) Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials(The Cochrane Library/Wiley)¹

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: The literature search was performed by an external collaborator, a librarian who was involved in clinical and epidemiological research and has extensive search experience in systematic review.

Date submitted: 2023/08/05

Date requested by: [Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

Search Topic or Title:

SGS (スルフォラファングルコシノレート) による肝機能の維持・改善作用

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s): (e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials

Database Platform(s): (e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

The Cochrane Library(Wiley)

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

健常成人を対象として、SGS を含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取と比較して、肝機能を維持・改善するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

P 健常成人

- I** SGS を含む食品の経口摂取
- C** 同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取
- O** 肝機能を維持・改善
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

```
#1 (sulforaphane NEXT glucosinolate*):ti,ab,kw in Trials 9
#2 ((broccoli NEXT seed NEXT extract*) OR (broccoli NEXT sprout*)):ti,ab,kw in Trials 135
#3 ("glucora phanin" OR glucoraphanin*):ti,ab,kw in Trials 58
#4 (sulforaphane):ti,ab,kw in Trials 212
#5 ("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphinylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphinylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane"):ti,ab,kw in Trials 214
#6 #4 OR #5 in Trials 214
#7 #2 AND #6 in Trials 92
#8 (glucoraphanin):ti,ab,kw in Trials 58
#9 #6 AND #8 in Trials 51
#10 (SFN AND SGS):ti,ab,kw in Trials 3
#11 #1 OR #7 OR #9 OR #10 in Trials 121
```

Key articles: 2018321874, 36618707=10.3389/fnut.2022.1077271(DOI)=CN-02550556(CENTRAL)

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Peer review was performed by an external collaborator, a medical librarian with extensive search experience in systematic review.

Date completed: 2023/08/17

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

1. Sulforaphane と glucoraphanin は類義語に近い捉え方で OR 検索ではいかがでしょうか。
2. 掛け合わせ等、全体の検索式は PubMed と共通の方針に合わせていただけたらと思います。

○#1 glucosinolate*との掛け合わせは、近接でない通常の AND 検索も可能でしょうか。

○#2 必要に応じて以下を足して広げる可能性が考えられます。

MeSH descriptor: [Brassicaceae] explode all trees

(cruciferous OR crucifera* OR broccoli* OR brassica*):ti,ab,kw

3. #3 が迷子と思われそうですが（意図的に残している？）、#8 と重複のようなのでいずれか一つで十分でしょうか。

¹The literature search and the peer review in this study were performed by two external Japanese collaborators; therefore, the suggestions and/or requests to each other were provided in Japanese.

4-5) CINAHL with Full Text (EBSCO)¹

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: The literature search was performed by an external collaborator, a librarian who was involved in clinical and epidemiological research and has extensive search experience in systematic review.

Date submitted: 2023/08/05

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

SGS（スルフォラファングルコシノレート）による肝機能の維持・改善作用

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s): (e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

CINAHL Plus with Full Text

Database Platform(s): (e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

EBSCOhost

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

健康成人を対象として、SGSを含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取と比較して、肝機能を維持・改善するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

P	健康成人
I	SGS を含む食品の経口摂取
C	同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取
O	肝機能を維持・改善
S	Click or tap here to enter text.
Inclusion Criteria	
(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]	
Click or tap here to enter text.	
Exclusion Criteria	
(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]	
Click or tap here to enter text.	
Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]	
<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. [mandatory if the answer was YES]	
Cochrane RCT filter (CINAHL 用を一部編集して使用)	
Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? [optional]	
Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. [mandatory]	
<p>*** sulforaphane glucosinolate ***</p> <p>S1 TX sulforaphane N0 glucosinolate* TX sulforaphane N0 glucosinolate* Search modes - Boolean/Phrase 18</p> <p>*** sulforaphane ***</p> <p>S2 TI (("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphinylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphinylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan* OR sulforaphane*)) OR AB (("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphinylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphinylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan* OR sulforaphane*)) Search modes - Boolean/Phrase 430</p> <p>S3 TX sulforaphane* Search modes - Boolean/Phrase 846</p> <p>S4 S2 OR S3 Search modes - Boolean/Phrase 847</p> <p>*** glucoraphanin とかけあわせ***</p> <p>S5 TI glucoraphanin* OR AB glucoraphanin* Search modes - Boolean/Phrase 50</p> <p>S6 S4 AND S5 Search modes - Boolean/Phrase 37</p> <p>*** ブロッコリーとかけあわせ***</p> <p>S7 TX ((broccoli W0 seed W0 extract*) OR (broccoli W0 sprout*)) Search modes - Boolean/Phrase 215</p> <p>S8 S4 AND S7 Search modes - Boolean/Phrase 127</p> <p>S9 S1 OR S4 OR S8 159</p>	

S10 ((MH ANIMALS+ NOT (MH HUMAN OR MH "Male")) OR (MH (ANIMAL STUDIES) NOT MH (HUMAN)) OR (TI (ANIMAL MODEL) NOT MH (HUMAN))) Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase
193,059 //Cochrane RCT filter を改変して一部使用

S11 S9 NOT S10 Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase 141

Key articles: 2018321874, 36618707, CN-02550556(CENTRAL)

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Peer review was performed by an external collaborator, a medical librarian with extensive search experience in systematic review. [Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

Date completed: 2023/08/19

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

[Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

[Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

Pubmed の検索式に合わせていただけたらと思います。

S2 "1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan* OR sulforaphane* OR sulphoraphane*
 S7 (MH "Cruciferous Vegetables+")も含めてご検討いただけたらありがたいです。

¹The literature search and the peer review in this study were performed by two external Japanese collaborators; therefore, the suggestions and/or requests to each other were provided in Japanese.

4-6) Global Index Medicus¹

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: The literature search was performed by an external collaborator, a librarian who was involved in clinical and epidemiological research and has extensive search experience in systematic review.

Date submitted: 2023/08/05

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

SGS (スルフォラファングルコシノレート) による肝機能の維持・改善作用

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s): (e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

African Index Medicus, Index Medicus for the Eastern Mediterranean Region, Index Medicus for the South-East Asia Region, Latin America and the Caribbean Literature on Health Sciences, Western Pacific Region Index Medicus

Database Platform(s): (e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Global Index Medicus

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

健常成人を対象として、SGSを含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取と比較して、肝機能を維持・改善するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

P 健常成人

- I SGS を含む食品の経口摂取
- C 同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取
- O 肝機能を維持・改善
- S Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)?
Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

```
1 tw:("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate") 0
2 tw:("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphinylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphinylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-
methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane") 78
3 tw:("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphinylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphinylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-
methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane") 78
4 tw:("broccoli seed extract" OR "broccoli seed extracts" OR "broccoli sprout" OR "broccoli sprouts") 6
```

Key articles: 2018321874, 36618707, CN-02550556(CENTRAL)

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Peer review was performed by an external collaborator, a medical librarian with extensive search experience in systematic review.

Date completed: 2023/08/19

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

#2 "1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphinylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphinylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane" OR glucoraphanin 件数増えませんが記載しておく？

#2, #3 検索式重複？

¹The literature search and the peer review in this study were performed by two external Japanese collaborators; therefore, the suggestions and/or requests to each other were provided in Japanese.

4-7) International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP)

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: The literature search was performed by an external collaborator, a librarian who was involved in clinical and epidemiological research and has extensive search experience in systematic review.

Date submitted: 2023/08/05

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

SGS (スルフォラファングルコシノレート) による肝機能の維持・改善作用

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s): (e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

ICTRP

Database Platform(s): (e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

健常成人を対象として、SGSを含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取と比較して、肝機能を維持・改善するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

- P** 健常成人
- I** SGS を含む食品の経口摂取
- C** 同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取
- O** 肝機能を維持・改善
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)?
Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

- 1 in the Title (Recruitment status:ALL) ("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate")
0
- 2 in the Title (Recruitment status:ALL) ("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphinylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphinylbutyl
Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane") 80 records
for 79 trials found!
- 3 in the Title (Recruitment status:ALL) ("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphinylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphinylbutyl
Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane") 51 records
for 51 trials found!
- 4 in the Intervention (Recruitment status:ALL) ("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate")
4 records for 4 trials found!
- 5 in the Intervention (Recruitment status:ALL) ("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate")
71 records for 69 trials found!
- 6 in the Intervention (Recruitment status:ALL) ("broccoli seed extract" OR "broccoli seed extracts" OR "broccoli
sprout" OR "broccoli sprouts") 54 records for 54 trials found!

Key articles: 2018321874, 36618707, CN-02550556(CENTRAL)

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Peer review was performed by an external collaborator, a medical librarian with extensive search experience in systematic review.

Date completed: 2023/08/19

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested

C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:
[Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

6. Limits and Filters

A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:
 Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):
[Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:
 #2, #5 は、"1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphinylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphinylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane" OR glucoraphanin 1件増えます。
 #3 は、"broccoli seed extract" OR "broccoli seed extracts" OR "broccoli sprout" OR "broccoli sprouts" の検索ですね。

¹The literature search and the peer review in this study were performed by two external Japanese collaborators; therefore, the suggestions and/or requests to each other were provided in Japanese.

4-8) International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO)¹

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher	
Searcher: The literature search was performed by an external collaborator, a librarian who was involved in clinical and epidemiological research and has extensive search experience in systematic review.	
Date submitted: 2023/08/05	Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.
Search Topic or Title:	
SGS (スルフォラファンゲルコシノレート) による肝機能の維持・改善作用	
This search strategy is:	
My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This is my first submission	<input type="checkbox"/> This is submitted after feedback
This search strategy is:	
My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This is my first submission	<input type="checkbox"/> This is submitted after feedback
Database(s): (e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): [mandatory]	
PROSPERO	
Database Platform(s): (e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): [mandatory]	
Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.	
*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:	
Research Question(s)	
(Describe the purpose of the search) [mandatory]	
健常成人を対象として、SGS を含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取と比較して、肝機能を維持・改善するか	
PICO(S) or Related Format	
(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)	
P	健常成人
I	SGS を含む食品の経口摂取

C 同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取

O 肝機能を維持・改善

S Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

Yes

No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

1	"sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate"	0
2	"1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphinylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphinylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane"	13
3	"broccoli seed extract" OR "broccoli seed extracts" OR "broccoli sprout" OR "broccoli sprouts"	1

Key articles: 2018321874, 36618707, CN-02550556(CENTRAL)

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Peer review was performed by an external collaborator, a medical librarian with extensive search experience in systematic review.

Date completed: 2023/08/17

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

#1,2 確認しました。ありがとうございます。

#3 broccoli* OR crucifer*も加えるのはいかがでしょうか。(広すぎる?)

¹The literature search and the peer review in this study were performed by two external Japanese collaborators; therefore, the suggestions and/or requests to each other were provided in Japanese.

4-9) ClinicalTrials.gov¹**Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher**

Searcher: The literature search was performed by an external collaborator, a librarian who was involved in clinical and epidemiological research and has extensive search experience in systematic review.

Date submitted: 2023/08/05

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

SGS (スルフォラファングルコシノレート) による肝機能の維持・改善作用

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s): (e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

ClinicalTrials.gov(classic)

Database Platform(s): (e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

健常成人を対象として、SGSを含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取と比較して、肝機能を維持・改善するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

P 健常成人

- I SGS を含む食品の経口摂取
- C 同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取
- O 肝機能を維持・改善
- S Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)?
Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

1 Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate")
26

2 Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphinylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphinylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane") AND glucoraphanin) 23

3 Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("broccoli seed extract" OR "broccoli seed extracts" OR "broccoli sprout" OR "broccoli sprouts") 65

4 Intervention/treatment (Recruitment status:ALL) ("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate") 20

5 Intervention/treatment (Recruitment status:ALL) ("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphinylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphinylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane") AND glucoraphanin) 18

6 Intervention/treatment (Recruitment status:ALL) ("broccoli seed extract" OR "broccoli seed extracts" OR "broccoli sprout" OR "broccoli sprouts") 59

Key articles: 2018321874, 36618707, CN-02550556(CENTRAL)

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Peer review was performed by an external collaborator, a medical librarian with extensive search experience in systematic review.

Date completed: 2023/08/19

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

#2, #5 末尾の箇所、OR glucoraphanin としてはいかがでしょうか。

#3, #6 brassica 等に広げるとノイズが多く増えるため、ご提案通りでよいかと思います。

¹The literature search and the peer review in this study were performed by two external Japanese collaborators; therefore, the suggestions and/or requests to each other were provided in Japanese.

4-10) University Hospital Medical Information Network-Clinical Trials Registry (UMIN-CTR)¹**Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher**

Searcher: The literature search was performed by an external collaborator, a librarian who was involved in clinical and epidemiological research and has extensive search experience in systematic review.

Date submitted: 2023/08/05

Date requested by: [Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

Search Topic or Title:

SGS (スルフォラファンゲルコシノレート) による肝機能の維持・改善作用

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s): (e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

UMIN-CTR

Database Platform(s): (e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

健常成人を対象として、SGSを含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取と比較して、肝機能を維持・改善するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

P 健常成人

I SGSを含む食品の経口摂取

C 同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取

O 肝機能を維持・改善

S Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

Yes

No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)?

Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

```

1      フリーワード検索：検索キーワード スルフォラファン グルコシノレート 2
2      フリーワード検索：検索キーワード sulforaphane glucosinolate 1
3      フリーワード検索：検索キーワード Sulphoraphane 0
4      フリーワード検索：スルフォラファン 17 //8/5
5      フリーワード検索：スルフォラフェン 0
6      フリーワード検索：ブロッコリスプラウト 2
7      フリーワード検索：BS 抽出物 0
8      検索：目的1 スルフォラファン グルコシノレート 1
9      検索：目的1 sulforaphane glucosinolate 1
10     検索：目的1 Sulphoraphane 0
11     検索：目的1 スルフォラファン 12
12     検索：目的1 スルフォラフェン 0
13     検索：目的1 ブロッコリスプラウト 1
14     検索：目的1 BS 抽出物 0

```

//計37(重複除去後18)

Key articles: 2018321874, 36618707

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Peer review was performed by an external collaborator, a medical librarian with extensive search experience in systematic review.

Date completed: 2023/08/18

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this

control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

トータル19件？

¹The literature search and the peer review in this study were performed by two external Japanese collaborators; therefore, the

suggestions and/or requests to each other were provided in Japanese.

Appendix 5. The list of the excluded reports.

No.	Author(s)	Journal(s)	Title	Reason(s)
1	Fuke, N; Ushida, Y.; Aoki, Y.; Suganuma, H.	Associate Journal of Japanese Society for Medical Use of Functional Foods	Sulforaphane, a broccoli-derived functional ingredient and its beneficial effects on fatty liver and glucose metabolism impairment	Review report (not original article)

<u>Study ID</u>	<u>D1</u>	<u>D2</u>	<u>D3</u>	<u>D4</u>	<u>D5</u>	<u>Overall</u>
Kikuchi 2018						
Satomi 2022						

Low risk

Some concerns

High risk

Appendix 6. The results of the risk of bias evaluation using RoB2 tool¹.

¹Abbreviations: D1, Randomization process; D2, Deviations from the intended interventions; D3, Missing outcome data; D4, Measurement of the outcome; D5, Selection of the reported result.

Appendix 7. Funnel plots for the serum hepatic biomarkers (ALT, AST, and γ -GTP)

Appendix8. The results of certainty assessment of the risk of bias across studies using GRADEpro¹.

Certainty assessment							No of patients (95% CI)	Certainty	Importance
No of studies	Study design	Risk of bias	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Other considerations			

ALT

2	RCT	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none ^a	Glucoraphanin: n = 75, Placebo: n = 65, MD [95% CI] : -2.91 [- 6.36, 0.55]	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High	
---	-----	-------------	-------------	-------------	-------------	-------------------	---	--------------	--

AST

2	RCT	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none ^b	Glucoraphanin: n = 75, Placebo: n = 65, MD [95% CI] : -1.19 [- 3.72, 1.34]	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High	
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γ-GTP

2	RCT	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none ^c	Glucoraphanin: n = 75, Placebo: n = 65, MD [95% CI] : 0.10 [- 4.17, 4.37]	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High	
---	-----	-------------	-------------	-------------	-------------	-------------------	--	--------------	--

¹Abbreviations: CI, confidence interval; MD, mean difference

^{a, b, c} Begg's test for a publication bias indicated a non-significant difference ($p = 0.32$), although we could not determine whether the bilateral symmetry in the funnel plot was confirmed due to the low number of included studies. Based on these results, we did not conclude that publication bias was strongly suspected.

Appendix 9. The quality assessment of the systematic review using the AMSTAR-2 criteria.

AMSTAR-2 criterion		Our review
Item 1	Did the research questions and inclusion criteria for the review include the components of PICO?	Yes
Item 2 [†]	Did the report of the review contain an explicit statement that the review methods were established prior to the conduct of the review and did the report justify any significant deviations from the protocol?	Yes
Item 3	Did the review authors explain their selection of the study designs for inclusion in the review?	Yes
Item 4 [†]	Did the review authors use a comprehensive literature search strategy?	Yes
Item 5	Did the review authors perform study selection in duplicate?	Yes
Item 6	Did the review authors perform data extraction in duplicate?	Yes
Item 7 [†]	Did the review authors provide a list of excluded studies and justify the exclusions?	Yes
Item 8	Did the review authors describe the included studies in adequate detail?	Yes
Item 9 [†]	Did the review authors use a satisfactory technique for assessing the risk of bias (RoB) in individual studies that were included in the review?	Yes
Item 10	Did the review authors report on the sources of funding for the studies included in the review?	Yes
Item 11 [†]	If meta-analysis was performed did the review authors use appropriate methods for statistical combination of results?	Yes
Item 12	If meta-analysis was performed, did the review authors assess the potential impact of RoB in individual studies on the results of the meta-analysis or other evidence synthesis?	Yes
Item 13 [†]	Did the review authors account for RoB in individual studies when interpreting/discussing the results of the review?	Yes
Item 14	Did the review authors provide a satisfactory explanation for, and discussion of, any heterogeneity observed in the results of the review?	Yes
Item 15 [†]	If they performed quantitative synthesis did the review authors carry out an adequate investigation of publication bias (small study bias) and discuss its likely impact on the results of the review?	Yes
Item 16	Did the review authors report any potential sources of conflict of interest, including any funding they received for conducting the review?	Yes
Total of "Yes"		16
The confidence in the results of the review [‡]		High

[†] AMSTAR 2 critical domain.

[‡] Rating overall confidence in the results of the review are categorized as follows: **High** - Zero or one non-critical weakness: The systematic review provides an accurate and comprehensive summary of the results of the available studies that address the question of interest; **Moderate** - More than one non-critical weakness*: The systematic review has more than one weakness, but no critical flaws. It may provide an accurate summary of the results of the available studies that were included in the review; **Low** - One critical flaw with or without non-critical weaknesses: The review has a critical flaw and may not provide an accurate and comprehensive summary of the available studies that address the question of interest; **Critically low** - More than one critical flaw with or without non-critical weaknesses: The review has more than one critical flaw and should not be relied on to provide an accurate and comprehensive summary of the available studies.

Appendix 10. The data of the serum hepatic biomarkers levels applied to the MA¹.

		Values between before and after the intervention [§]										
		Glucoraphanin group				Placebo group				<i>P</i> value [†]	<i>P</i> value [‡]	Ref.
	N	Before	After	MD	N	Before	After	MD				
ALT	40	28.7 ± 8.8	25.9 ± 12.0	(-2.9 ± 10.6)	30	25.7 ± 8.7	24.4 ± 9.2	(-1.3 ± 8.2)	<i>p</i> > 0.05	<i>p</i> > 0.05	[35]	
	35	(36.0 ± 9.1)	(30.4 ± 9.0)	(-5.6 ± 10.4)	35	(35.9 ± 10.8)	(35.3 ± 13.6)	(-0.6 ± 13.2)	<i>p</i> = 0.041	(<i>p</i> = 0.075)	[36]	
AST	40	24.8 ± 5.2	24.7 ± 8.3	(-0.1 ± 8.8)	30	24.8 ± 6.4	25.8 ± 8.1	(1.0 ± 5.7)	<i>p</i> > 0.05	<i>p</i> > 0.05	[35]	
	35	(27.5 ± 7.4)	(27.1 ± 7.6)	(-0.4 ± 7.2)	35	(28.5 ± 8.5)	(29.3 ± 10.1)	(0.9 ± 8.9)	<i>p</i> = 0.348	(<i>p</i> = 0.338)	[36]	
γ-GTP	40	33.2 ± 15.9	31.9 ± 23.9	(-1.4 ± 15.2)	30	30.1 ± 17.3	27.2 ± 17.2	(-2.9 ± 5.4)	<i>p</i> > 0.05	<i>p</i> > 0.05	[35]	
	35	(39.1 ± 19.9)	(39.4 ± 23.1)	(0.3 ± 15.3)	35	(48.0 ± 26.0)	(51.5 ± 28.0)	(3.5 ± 18.0)	<i>p</i> = 0.088	(<i>p</i> = 0.349)	[36]	

¹ Abbreviations: ALT, alanine aminotransferase; AST, aspartate aminotransferase; γ-GTP, gamma-glutamyltransferase; MD, mean difference. The values in parentheses mean those obtained from inquiries to the authors.

[§] Data are presented as mean ± standard deviation.

[†] The difference of the actual values after the intervention between groups.

[‡] The difference of the change values after the intervention between groups.

Appendix 11. The data of the serum hepatic biomarkers levels for the MA according to the subgroup analysis ¹.

Values between before and after the intervention [§]											
Glucoraphanin group				Placebo group				P value [†]	P value [‡]	Ref.	
n	Before	After	MD	n	Before	After	MD				
ALT	9	37.0 ± 4.3	23.0 ± 6.1	(-14.0 ± 5.6)	5	36.8 ± 2.4	31.8 ± 9.4	(-5.0 ± 9.6)	<i>p</i> > 0.05	<i>p</i> < 0.05	[35]
	35	(36.0 ± 9.1)	(30.4 ± 9.0)	(-5.6 ± 10.4)	35	(35.9 ± 10.8)	(35.3 ± 13.6)	(-0.6 ± 13.2)	<i>p</i> = 0.041	(<i>p</i> = 0.075)	[36]
AST	9	28.8 ± 3.7	23.1 ± 4.3	(-5.7 ± 4.7)	5	31.0 ± 3.7	35.0 ± 11.3	(4.0 ± 7.9)	<i>p</i> < 0.05	(<i>p</i> < 0.05)	[35]
	35	(27.5 ± 7.4)	(27.1 ± 7.6)	(-0.4 ± 7.2)	35	(28.5 ± 8.5)	(29.3 ± 10.1)	(0.9 ± 8.9)	<i>p</i> = 0.348	(<i>p</i> = 0.338)	[36]
γ-GTP	9	40.7 ± 11.4	32.2 ± 14.3	(-8.4 ± 12.6)	5	52.6 ± 29.4	48.6 ± 29.2	(-4.0 ± 3.7)	<i>p</i> > 0.05	(<i>p</i> > 0.05)	[35]
	35	(39.1 ± 19.9)	(39.4 ± 23.1)	(0.3 ± 15.3)	35	(48.0 ± 26.0)	(51.5 ± 28.0)	(3.5 ± 18.0)	<i>p</i> = 0.088	(<i>p</i> = 0.349)	[36]

¹ Abbreviations: ALT, alanine aminotransferase; AST, aspartate aminotransferase; γ-GTP, gamma-glutamyltransferase; MD, mean difference. The values in parentheses mean those obtained from inquiries to the authors.

[§] Data are presented as mean ± standard deviation.

[†] The difference of the actual values after the intervention between groups.

[‡] The difference of the change values after the intervention between groups.